
Non-Governmental Organisations, Human Rights, and Gender Imbalance: Examination and Role of the United Nations

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ABSTRACT

Human Right is a controversial concept ambiguous to many. For many leaders or policy makers, it is as confusing and misleading to those who claim to be it adhere followers. For instance, non-seem to want to understand the exact doctrine that governs Human Rights.

The paper relied on both primary and secondary sources. The primary sources would be based on oral interviews and archival materials. Secondary sources on the other hand, were included in literatures such as books and newspapers. The oral interviews would be recorded and transcribed for analysis. The documentary data would be subjected to internal and external criticism for authentication and then to textual and contextual analysis

The paper contributed to knowledge through concepts such as Human Rights, which was unique in the 20st century.

KEYWORDS: Human Right, Natural Rights, Declaration, Education, United Nations.

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INTRODUCTION

Many of the most intractable problems (ranging from pandemics to the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction) are transnational in scope; and addressing them successfully requires action that is not only multilateral (involving more than two states) but also global. The policy authority and resource capacity necessary for tackling such problems, however, remains vested in states rather than in the United Nations. Established in 1945 by sovereign states seeking to protect themselves against external aggression, the UN was not built to confront many of the challenges that face the world today. The disconnect between the nature of a growing number of problems and the nature of the UN goes a long way toward explaining the world organization's recurrent difficulties on many fronts and the often-fitful nature of what essentially are tactical and short-term responses to challenges that require strategic transnational thinking and sustained global attention.

The logic of the system of world politics continues to reflect the basic principle of sovereign jurisdiction, which has its roots in the 1648 Peace of Westphalia (Calvocoressi, 1968). Only those rules consented to, and only those organizations voluntarily accepted, exist in interstate relations. Sovereignty, constructed to produce order and to buttress central authority within the state, also means that central authority remained underdeveloped. All territorial states came to be seen as equal in the sense of having ultimate authority to prescribe what "should be" in their jurisdictions: and sovereign equality is the most essential building block of world organization as spelled out in Article 2 of the UN Charter (or constitution). Interstate relations reflect what political scientists label "anarchy"-no overarching authority exists beyond that of individual states (Hedley, 2007). In the history of international relations and despite the notion of the sovereign equality of states, of course, all sorts of unequal relations have existed and have even been formally approved. In this sense, the fact that the five permanent members of the Security Council Permanent Five, each possess the veto follows many examples of inequality. Indeed, the wide spread exceptions and routine violations have led Stephen Krasner to characterize the notion of sovereignty as "organized hypocrisy. (Ibrahim & Haruna, 2014)"

The perpetuation of state sovereignty-the idea that each state has absolute authority over a given population and territory and should be free from outside interference-as the essential organizing principle provides obvious benefits within the international system

(Hosti, 2004). It affords newer, smaller, and less powerful states an equal legal footing and a seat at the international table with older or more powerful states. It also guarantees some order and predictability within what Hedley Bull and the members of the English School call "international society (Hedley, 2007)." Indeed, they see state sovereignty as not only a functional but also a political value that allows national societies to make choices and keep international organizations accountable (Hedley, 2007).

Moreover, international co-operation exists as a result of agreements among sovereign states-letters are delivered flights take off and land, trade grows steadily-but it falls far short of giving international organizations the wherewithal override decisions by states that fail to abide by the term of their agreements or that simply opt out. The agreement in the UN Charter not to use military force except with authorization from the Security Council or in selfdefense, for example, is ignored with few consequences for those who do so. Nevertheless, as the peoples and states of the world become more materially and morally interconnected, the need for more effective international management increases. Terrorism, economic crises, refugee movements, nuclear proliferation, and climate change all pose threats that are global in scope and cannot be adequately addressed by states acting individually to protect only their own citizens or territory. In today's world of near instantaneous global travel, to halt the spread of an infectious disease within its own territory, a state must also expend a certain amount of energy and resources on preventing the spread of disease in other states. Some may view such action as a moral imperative, but it is equally a practical necessity.

As peoples and states become not just interconnected but interdependent (meaning that their relations become sensitive enough that their own welfare is substantially affected by the decisions of others), demands often increase for more robust international management, which causes notions of state sovereignty to adapt. Americans are interconnected with "Hondurans" concerning trade in bananas; but Americans can do without the fruit or easily find alternate sources of supply. By contrast, in 1990 Americans were interdependent with Kuwaitis concerning trade in oil. As such, this relationship was far more sensitive because energy is a necessity for which alternate suppliers are not numerous and the rapidly rising costs of finding such a supplier would have caused a major disruption in American society and the world economy. As a result of interdependence, some issues that were formerly considered domestic and inconsequential have come to be redefined as international and significant because of the strength of transnational concerns of either a material or a moral nature. Still, even in the context of interdependence, most states are reluctant to transfer authority to international organizations, and certainly to the United Nations.

METHODOLOGY

The paper relied on both prime and derivative sources. The principal sources would be based on unpublished and archival materials. The primal sources would be investigated and defined for analysis. Secondary sources on the other hand, were included in literatures such as books and newspapers. The documentary data would be subjected to internal and external criticism for authentication and then to textual and contextual analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights published in 1948. Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charges against him. It also said that everyone charged with a penal offence has the right to be presumed innocent until proved guilty according to law in a public trial at which he has had all the guarantees necessary for his defence (Morsink, 1999). The Declaration emphasized that no one shall be held guilty of any penal offence, under national or international law, at the time when it was committed. Nor shall a heavier penalty be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time the penal offence was committed. The practicality of this declaration is another matter altogether. In furtherance signatories were reluctant to put this declaration to practice despite the fact that by their signatures on the documents it could only mean that they must support it (Morsink, 1999).

For some countries in Africa and Asia; Europe had again used the tool of Human Rights to reshape the new order as it once did reshaping the old order. For them, such principles always turn out to be derived from the Western European tradition which they assumed as greedy, oppressive, brutal and exploitative. Europeans, however, sees the Human Right Declaration as objectively improving, beneficent and humane for the modern society. According to the

Europeans, superiority was clearly proven when the Aztec and Inca civilizations couldn't stand toe to toe with the Spanish; Hindu, Africa and Chinese civilizations were arguably weaker to the European civilizations in the 15th century. Such statements can be true or untrue: but the facts are neither admirable nor repugnant. However, they register the fact that Europe reshaped an old and made the modern, world. Some Western ideas are still resented and resisted. Women for instance are still treated as unequal in some Christian and Islamic societies. In a system built on patriarchy, the fight for gender equality seems like a fight with a wavering lion with just human hands. You can say, Women are voting, they are working, competing with men in places of work, and the right to education. The quest for Human Rights had further pushed the figure for female stands at about 88% but there is an harsher truth hidden in this, millions of girls in continents such as Africa and Asia are still out of school and some even struggle to pay for basic education fees. Women for instance tend to feel that they have rights as citizens of these countries. Basic Human Rights such as:

- Right to Education
- Right to freedom of speech
- Right to fair hearing
- Right to Life
- Right to freedom of movement etc

Despite the above Rights, why do women still suffer from these rights? According to an author, she wrote “We should all be feminists” describes “Feminist as a person who believes in the social, political, and economic equality of the sexes. (Jane, 2005)” Now sexes is a general term, which simply activates the necessity of both parties to work together to achieve a more balanced society without no deformity. How then can we fully establish this in a setting of fake gender advocates under the covering of Misogynistic attitude, how can we move forward with strongholds of the mindset that sees slavery as submission? How can we step into a more balanced community that has men and women with equal rights? If we start fighting the strongholds of our mindset, maybe just maybe Human Rights will be an activity in the present and not an assignment. Human Right well analyzed contexts a proper balance in human society.

In the UN's human rights theater, as elsewhere, the dramatis personae are mainly states whose national selfinterests dominate their performances. While international civil servants and NGOs are actively trying to improve publicity and account ability, nonetheless the limelight is on states whose behavior makes or breaks human rights codification and enforcement. Various double standards and inconsistencies are well documented in the Commission on Human Rights between 1946 and 2006-and have not been significantly different in the Human Rights Council since then (Donnelly, Sovereign Inequality and Hierachy in Anarchy American Power and International Society). The United States at times focused on rights violations in Cuba, but disproportionately to events actually taking place there, especially when compared to more serious rights violations in allied states like Guatemala and El Salvador. Washington had long used human rights criticism as a political weapon to try to delegitimize the Castro government. Similarly during the Cold War, the Soviet Union was openly opportunistic in the commission, using human rights as a weapon against such US 'allies rights closer to home-in the Soviet as Augusto Pinochet's Chile but remaining silent about major violations of human closer to home- in the Soviet Union itself and in other communist bloc states (Hosti, 2004). Human rights language was put at the service of ideological and strategic calculations in the global South as well. Most developing countries paid far more attention to violate by well-known pariahs-Israel, or the white- minority regimes of Rhodesia and South Africa--rather than to similarly egregious ones in Idi Amin's Uganda or Pol Pot's Kampuchea (Calvocoressi, 1968). In short, many heads of state and government have their own versions of the quote attributed to US president Franklin D. Roosevelt about a Central American strongman: "Somoza may be a son of a bitch, but he's our son of a bitch." (Calvocoressi, 1968)

The promotion of human rights is one of the key elements and organizing principles in UN Charter Articles 1, 55, and 56. While member states commit themselves to the promotion of fundamental protections, the concept of universal human rights remains contested. Developing out of the western liberal tradition of "natural rights," human rights have often been labeled as "western imperialism," and criticized for placing too much emphasis on the rights of individuals at the expense of communities (Ignatieff, 2001). While this is not new-utilitarian theorist such as Jeremy Bentham criticized early proponents of natural rights such as John Locke and Thomas Hobbes for their promotion of individualism--the inability to move beyond a simplistic and ritualized North-South pattern is debilitating ailment (Leroy, 1980).

In 1948, governments were divided over the issue of universality while drafting the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The West argued for the primacy of civil and political rights, which are also referred to as "negative" rights because governments have to refrain from attacking them. Meanwhile, the East stressed the importance of economic, social, and cultural rights, which are also called "positive" rights because governments have to initiate steps to ensure that they are implemented (Ignatieff, 2001). The failure to reach consensus on this issue ultimately led to drafting two separate additional treaties in 1966--the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR--that put more flesh on the bones of the Universal Declaration and created mechanisms for implementation, monitoring, and enforcement (Ignatieff, 2001). Perhaps, an athletic image would help complement my theatrical one. To a large extent, within the UN, until the late 1980 human rights were an Ideological football (or soccer ball) kicked back and forth in an international game between East and West (Harari, Homo Deus: A Brief History of Tomorrow, 2017). Western players wore the colors of political and civil rights, Eastern players those of economic and social rights. Depending on their political affiliations, southern players actively joined one team or the other on the playing field or cheered from the sidelines for whoever seemed to be in the lead (Jane, 2005). The international game was mainly a shouting match with lots of attack and denunciation but little attention to the practical problems and issues that were often high on domestic agendas at the time, and that could have been ameliorated by sharing lessons and exploring new approaches. Only as the Cold War was beginning to de-escalate, and groups concerned with the rights of women and children entered the stadium, did the game and playing field change.

Progress in human rights has, nonetheless, been nothing short of remarkable. The original idea has made substantial inroads into policy and legislation. Beginning in the 1980s, a surge of ratifications of human rights conventions occurred, along with increasing implementation of many measures and outrage over abuses. About three-quarters of UN member states have now ratified the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, a kind of international bill of rights for women. However, only the United States and Somalia have not ratified the Convention on the Rights of the Child. This is largely due to their unwillingness to renounce capital punishment or the recruitment of soldiers 18 years of age below.

The universality of human rights had come from part of the global South. The first is the concept of "Asian values"-the assertion that the continent's cultures value the well-being of the community over that of the individual and exhibit a natural respect for authority. The Asian values argument has been used to justify enduring authoritarian institutions despite trends toward greater political liberalization in many parts of the globe. The second is the "trade-off theory-which developing countries should be allowed to neglect human rights in their pursuit of development until they are able to "catch up to the West. Invoking the relatively successful economic performance of countries such as South Korea, Singapore, and China over the past few decades, supporters argue that the suppression of political and economic rights is necessary for robust growth. The debate has played out in bitter exchanges between the North and South in General Assembly discussions, with those parts of the South that disagree very often reluctant to break ranks. Continuing with the theme of human rights protection more generally will be helpful to our understanding of the implications of UN feudalism. Institutional concerns with turf have prevented the establishment of a central organization for Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs). The same reflex against consolidation has led to a different manifestation of the same problem elsewhere. For humanitarian action-delivering emergency relief and protecting the human rights of war victims-there is not really a shortage but a surfeit of actors. The key problem is the lack of concerted action by a host of players within the UN system as well as a parallel universe of NGOs that function as UN subcontractors. The plethora of NGOs, whose numbers continue to grow makes the combined UN-private humanitarian system ever more unwieldy. The enterprise is atomized". Competitive individual units, rather than working as partners, often end up "defecting" from a common approach because it is in of course, in the interests of the victims of natural disasters, repression and war. Some of the growth in the last two decades reflects a creative adaptation to the crises growing from the new wars, but some of it simply reflects institutional expansion and empire building. And this reality frames the peculiar collective action problems of the new humanitarianisms.

To begin, there is a fundamental absence of longitudinal data regarding basic categories such as expenditure, income, number of organizations, and activities. Nonetheless, there is evidence that the humanitarian sector has undergone significant change since the end of the Cold War-most noticeable in its population density, resources, and activities. There has been tremendous growth in the sheer number of humanitarian organizations. How much? This depends on who counts and who is worth counting. Most surveys automatically include nonprofit relief agencies. Presently there are an estimated 2,500 NGOs in the humanitarian business, but only about 260 are serious players based on a 2003 online source. This figure excludes NGOs not engaged in relief or the myriad mom-and-pop organizations that crop up around specific agencies. In 2001, the half-dozen or so largest NGOs controlled between \$2.5 billion and \$3 billion, or between 45 percent and 55 percent of total humanitarian assistance. Half a decade later, the so called Big 8 (World Vision; Save the Children; Catholic Relief Services; CARE; MSE; Oxfam; the IRC, and Mercy Corps) garnered the lion's share of the market with an estimated 70 percent of relief funding.

A 2006 survey of US-based private voluntary agencies which offers a reasonably good picture that typify growth over the last 70 years in a number of wealthy countries, In 1940, at the start of World War II, the number rose to 387 (from 240) organizations, but the number dropped to 103 in 1946 and 60 in 1948. The number grew rapidly in from 1986-2005 (from 178 to 543). Not only has the total number increased but so too have the dimensions of the largest among them. The dozen or so that represent the bulk of aid programming and personnel have all been in existence for some time. In addition, dramatic crises often account for spikes in the numbers of smaller agencies on the ground. For over 200 international NGOs were reported to have mailboxes instance, in Sarajevo and Kigali. The numbers of people working for the NGO component of the humanitarian sector grew by 91 percent from 1997 to 2005, while overall the international humanitarian system (if the UN system and the ICRC are also included) experienced a 77 percent surge in personnel.

But even these figures may potentially undercount the number of aid agencies and personnel because of tendency to focus on those based in the West. To some this bias accurately reflects the origins of the bulk of resources and institutions. Yet there is also a very active relief sector in the non-western world, most obviously in Islamic countries the location for about half of the victims of war since the beginning of the 1990s. There is more speculation than concrete knowledge; because of September 11, 2001, attention is directed less at understanding than connecting Islamic charitable organization and terrorism. Lack of coordination and overlapping jurisdiction among multiple UN agencies has also hindered the UN's effectiveness at promoting women's empowerment, which has considerable ramifications for women and for the planet. Such goals as reproductive rights; fair labor remuneration; access, participation, and representation in political institutions; and education are important ends in themselves but also have a direct impact on environmental sustainability and development. These concerns touch upon global threats including overpopulation, the

spread of HIV/AIDS, poverty, and pollution. In the words of the 1985 Nairobi Forward-Looking Strategy: "without advancement of women, development itself will be difficult to achieve. Despite the gravity of women's issues, the UN has lacked a central agency that can effectively work toward generating normative consensus and practical policies. Until 2011, responsibility was dispersed among several UN bodies including the UN Population Fund (UNFPA), the Commission on the status of Women (CSW), the UN Secretariat's own Division for the Advancement of Women (DAW) as well as the Office of the Special Advisor to the secretary-general on Gender Issues and the Advancement of Women (OSAGI), the UN International Research and Training Institute for the Advancement of Women (INSTRAW), and the UN Development Fund for Women (UNIFEM) (Charlotte, 2007).

In spite of this long list of acronyms, readers should not assume that women's issues are at the top of the agenda or even well-resourced. As Rutgers University's Charlotte Bunch summarizes, "women-specific work has largely remained marginalized, and the small resources and power invested in it has plagued efforts to achieve implementation of the high standards repeatedly espoused on this topic. None of them—with the exception of UNFPA—comes close to qualifying as an agency with substantial resources and reach, to be mentioned in the same breath as UNICEF or the UN Refugee Agency UNHCR. Established in 1966 as the UN Fund for Population Activities with funding beginning in 1969, the name was shortened to the UN Population Fund after the 1999 International Conference on Population and Development in Cairo. It is the world's largest international source of funding for population and reproductive health program working with governments and NGOs in over 140 countries on programs that help women as well as men and young people.

The Commission on the status of Women (CSW) was established in 1946 as a subsidiary body of the Commission on Human Rights to be the UN's primary intergovernmental policy recommendations and reports for ECOSOC. Its impact is helped by drawing on NGOs, but the commission resources are truly meager, and it only met every other year until 1987 (Jane, 2005). The four UN world conferences on women (in Mexico City in 1975, Copenhagen in 1980, Nairobi in 1985 and Beijing in 1995) transformed in many ways the work of the CSW, which has met annually since 1987. The Division for the Advancement of Women (DAW) was the name of the UN Secretariat's unit that provided substantive support for the CSW. Its work included mainstreaming gender perspectives as well as providing substantive and technical servicing to the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women. It was formerly housed in the Department of Economic and Social Affairs.

The Office of the Special Advisor to the secretary-general on Gender Issues and the Advancement of Women (OSAGI) resulted from a recommendation made at Beijing in 1995 that there should be a senior official taking a leadership role on gender mainstreaming and reporting directly to the secretary-general. The office also attempted to improve the status of women within the secretariat itself. The UN International Research and Training Institute for the Advancement of Women (INSTRAW) was established following the first World Conference on the International Women's Year in Mexico in 1975, and its operations moved to the Dominican Republic in 1983. Its research concentrates on technical issues (for example, attaching a specific value to women's household work). INSTRAW conducts training seminars and has elaborated training materials on gender and development. UN Development Fund for Women UNIFEM also resulted from the Mexico conference and began as the Voluntary Fund for the UN Decade for Women in 1976 to promote what the decade's subtitle called "equality, development and peace". It served as a catalyst for activities within the UN system and the national level as well. In 1948 it became a separate operational entity and was renamed UNIFEM and associated with the UNDP. In addition to head-quarters in New York, it had 15 regional offices and was linked to UN development activities through UNDP projects at country level in many developing countries.

UNIFEM had a mandate to support initiatives that benefit women and to bring women into mainstream development activities. It focused on reducing feminized poverty and violence; reversing the spread of HIV/AIDS among women and girls; and achieving gender equality in democratic governance. But it failed to serve as an effective coordinating body for the issues relating to women. The High-level Panel on Coherence's 2006 *Delivering as one* identified the need for a more robust entity in the UN's "gender architecture" to deal with women's issues in a more structured and coordinated fashion. Most of 2007 was spent deliberating—not about the merit of strengthening the UN's work on women's rights and the consolidation of its gender architecture, but rather about who was going to get what and which person would head the institution. The predictable result was foot-dragging until July 2010 and the creation of UN Women, the United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women.

The decision to create UN Women was an encouraging institutional breakthrough of sorts. Previously, no formal UN institution had ever been shuttered as an anachronism and UN Women consolidated four previously weak and autonomous units (UNIFEM OSAGI, TRAW, and the Division for the advancement of Women). It would have been an even more crucial precedent and the precedent also folded the UN Population Fund (UNFPA) and avoided creating yet another governing body. Billed as an effort to pool resources and mandates, the new UN women was not empowered with UNFPA's resources, the largest operational agency with an impact on women's lives and it created yet another executive board (albeit with non-traditional donors). Is it not possible to consolidate executive boards? Do we really require an eleventh one specifically to engage in gender theological disputes?

Is the glass half full or empty? Charlotte Bunch answers: "On the one hand, there has been much progress since women first fought for their inclusion in the UN Charter; on the other hand, after sixty years of struggle, one could expect more as well from the world

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body whose power depends on its moral authority (Jane, 2005)." Part of the reason for the emptiness of the world organization's gender glass is the continued tolerance of separate, disparate, and feudal fiefdoms for the efforts on behalf of women instead of a passionate commitment to do what is necessary to consolidate and get the most for women from the United Nations (Jane, 2005).

One might have expected the UN to be taking the lead at integrating women into its workforce compared with other institutions, and faster than many of its member states. While efforts have been made to achieve an equitable gender balance in the world body, the rate of progress has been glacial. Indeed, from the outset, women have had to challenge patriarchal norms and institutions, and much of their work on peace and security issues was separated from the UN's mainstream activities in its early years.

Eleanor Roosevelt, first chair of the Commission on Human Rights, was a pioneer, and in February 1946, in her "Open Letter to the Women of the World," she made a direct appeal for women to be involved in peace efforts, asserting the UN provided a window of opportunity for them to do .

Some three decades later, at the first UN-sponsored world conference on women held in 1975 in Mexico City, governments signed the Declaration of Mexico, which proclaimed: "Women must participate equally with men in the decision making processes which help to promote peace at all levels " That same year, the General Assembly called upon women to participate in the process of strengthening international peace and security in resolution.

CONCLUSION

At the beginning of the twenty-first century, however, women continue to be excluded from the front lines in this area, as illustrated by the paltry participation of women in UN peace operations at all levels. Over the last two decades, there has been an overall increase in female participation from 1 percent of uniformed personnel in 1993 to 3 percent of military and 9 percent of police in 2011, however, remain absurdly low. More specifically, women account for a mere 3.33 percent of peacekeeping personnel worldwide while they constitute about 30 percent of civilian staff for missions; this is about the level they had attained some decades ago. The current condition of women in the UN administration as a whole is disappointing. The representation of women in the professional and higher categories in the UN system is 39.9 percent. Only at the entry-P-1 and P-2 professional levels has gender balance been achieved. In the categories-D-1 and above-women make up 23 and 29 percent of UN staff. Moreover, in an arena much flexibility-the appointment of special representatives of the Secretary General (SRSGs) the results also remain poor. At the highest level-that of the secretary-general's special and personal representative and envoys statistics are not

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